

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases

Base 11 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations:

5491_{10}	4142_{11}	378_{10}	314_{11}
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^6_{11}+7_{11}*89A$		$A9_{11}^{(8_{11}-7_{11})}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6_{10}+7_{10}*1077_{10}$	$119_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$
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Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	A	+	-	*	/	^	()
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	-----

Digits 1 up to A occur in increasing or decreasing order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A$	$A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Digits represent single-digit or multi-digit numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A$	$A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Numbers occur in positive form or negative form (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A$	$A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Allowed operations; addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and/or exponentiation.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A$	$A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Order of evaluation may be influenced by parentheses (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A$	$A9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Representations with negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45*(6^7)+8-9A)$	$(A98+7*(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9A)$	$(A98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9A)$	$(A98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(-(1+2)+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9A)$	$(A98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9))*A)$	$-(A*(9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Identify genuine base 11 crazy sequential representations for 0000_{11} up to $AAAA_{11}$

Expected number of representations = $2_{11} + AAAA_{11} + AAAA_{11} = 20000_{11} = 29282_{10}$

Results

29164₁₀ out of 29282₁₀ were identified, see supplement.

Missing

Increasing	7A88, 8473, 8536, 8550, 8594, 85AA, 8770, 8776, 8A80, 8A97, 8AA0, 94A4, 9577, 9585, 9600, 9607, 9652, 9721, 9751, 9753, 9787, 9807, 9833, 9839, 9850, 985A, A248, A257, A331, A440, A454, A568, A5A2, A655, A720, A989
Decreasing	7361, 7486, 769A, 7794, 7A25, 7A43, 7A73, 8054, 8056, 8086, 8094, 80A3, 8136, 8150, 8159, 8178, 8386, 8565, 8599, 89A5, 8A41, 8A91, 9085, 9150, 91A2, 9229, 9382, 9412, 9486, 9487, 9494, 94A3, 94A4, 94A6, 9544, 954A, 9550, 9555, 9570, 9586, 95A3, 95A4, 95A9, 9625, 9647, 9648, 9707, 9727, 9A04, 9A12, 9AA3, 9AA7, A007, A03A, A045, A094, A097, A144, A158, A159, A371, A378, A408, A467, A477, A482, A483, A48A, A499, A531, A547, A561, A619, A651, A666, A680, A736, A737, A75A, A763, A769, A835

Notes

Authors consider base 11 crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

Other Bases

Authors also identified genuine crazy sequential representations for other bases:

Date	Title
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

References

1. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v1>
Natural Numbers from 44 to 1000 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 6 Feb 2013.
2. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v2>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 44 to 4444 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Tuesday 19 Mar 2013
3. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v3>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 1 to 11111 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 5 Jun 2013
4. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v4>
More on Crazy Sequential Representation of Natural Numbers with Subtraction
Inder J. Taneja. Monday 5 Aug 2013
5. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479v5>
Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 0 to 11111 in terms of
Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 8 Jan 2014
6. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6483968>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1288822>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Tuesday 12 Jun 2018
7. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6516131>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1288892>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Thursday 14 Jun 2018
8. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6587117>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1292115>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 18 Jun 2018
9. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a108.pdf>
MD5: BB89800FB86BDF830D28EB07241D78C1
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000
Inder J. Taneja. Wednesday 12 Sep 2018

10. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a131.pdf>
MD5: D135C0F9A417B7221AEBB1225FDF7B8D
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000
Inder J. Taneja. Saturday 10 Nov 2018
11. <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a132.pdf>
MD5: 87BF426B1827555F5FB701F7DAE33969
Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000
Inder J. Taneja. Saturday 10 Nov 2018
12. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7429967>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1998118>
Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Thursday 06 Dec 2018
13. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7467665>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2276623>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 14 Dec 2018
14. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7505690>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2525823>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Monday 24 Dec 2018
15. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7539311>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530025>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 02 Jan 2019
16. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.05070v1>
Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases
Tim Wylie. Thursday 11 Oct 2018
17. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546955>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530974>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
18. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546958>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530976>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
19. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546970>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530978>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019

20. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546982>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530980>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019

21. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546985>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530982>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019

22. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7546991>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530984>
Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019